

Some Silver(I) Complexes Containing Neutral Bidentate Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Silver nitrate was reacted with α - α' -dipyridyl, 6-phenanthroline, 2:9 dimethyl 6-phenanthroline and 4:7 diphenyl 6-phenanthroline in ethanolic medium and compounds having the composition $[\text{Ag}(\text{dipy})\text{NO}_3]$, $[\text{Ag}(\text{Phen})_2]\text{NO}_3$, $[\text{Ag}(\text{dime. phen})]\text{NO}_3$ and $[\text{Ag}(\text{diph. phen})]\text{NO}_3$ were isolated and characterised. The dipyridyl complex is a three-coordinated one with coordinated nitrate group. The 6-phenanthroline complex is tetra-coordinated with an ionic nitrate group and the rest are apparently two-coordinated compounds. Infra-red spectra support the formulation.

UNIVALENT silver forms two¹, three^{2,3} and four^{4,5} coordinated complexes utilising sp , sp^2 or sp^3 hybrid bonding orbitals. In some complexes, besides the ligands used, some anions like nitrate, thiocyanate and perchlorate also coordinate with the metal ion. Several three-coordinated silver I complexes having the formula AgL_2NO_3 containing a monodentate nitrogen donor ligand, L and a coordinated nitrate group were reported² earlier. In this communication, the reaction of silver nitrate with neutral bidentate nitrogen donor ligands like α - α' -dipyridyl(dipy), 1:10 6-phenanthroline (phen), 2:9 dimethyl 6-phenanthroline (dime. phen) and 4:7 diphenyl 6-phenanthroline (diph. phen) was studied and reported.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Reactions were studied in absolute alcohol medium. Silver nitrate and the ligands were taken in the stoichiometric ratio (either 1:1 or 1:2) and were dissolved in absolute ethanol. The hot ethanolic solutions on mixing and vigorous stirring gave rise to solid products which were suction filtered, washed and dried *in vacuo*. The dipyridyl complex is crystalline and is soluble in acetone and other organic solvents whereas the other complexes are amorphous and are soluble only in nitrobenzene. The conductance

measurements were carried out on $M/1000$ solutions in nitrobenzene using a Toshniwal Conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The infra-red absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. Analytical, melting point and conductance data are given in Table 1 and the infra-red absorption bands pertaining to nitrate group are returned in Table 2.

TABLE 2. INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1}) PERTAINING TO NITRATE GROUP IN SILVER (I) COMPLEXES

$[\text{Ag}(\text{dipy})\text{NO}_3]$	$[\text{Ag}(\text{phen})_2]\text{NO}_3$	$[\text{Ag}(\text{dime. phen})]\text{NO}_3$	$[\text{Ag}(\text{diph. phen})]\text{NO}_3$
800 (s)	750 (s)	755 (s)	720 (s)
950 (m)	830 (s)	835 (m)	820 (s)
990 (m)	1275 (s)	1285 (vs)	1222 (s)
1155 (s)	1590 (s)	—	1520 (m)

s-sharp, vs-very sharp, m-medium

Discussion

All the compounds reported are diamagnetic as required for completely filled 4d non-boding shell of silver I. The molar conductance, Λ_M , value of

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL, MELTING POINT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF SILVER COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour and form	M.P. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	% Silver		Λ_M (mhos)
			Found	Required	
$[\text{Ag}(\text{dipy})\text{NO}_3]$	White crystalline	148	32.6	33.0	0.5
$[\text{Ag}(\text{phen})_2]\text{NO}_3$	Light brown amorphous	>300	19.4	19.1	26.1
$[\text{Ag}(\text{dime. phen})]\text{NO}_3$	White amorphous	>300	28.1	28.5	186
$[\text{Ag}(\text{diph. phen})]\text{NO}_3$	Pale yellow amorphous	>300	22.2	21.3	18.6

dipyridyl complex is very low (0.5 mhos) indicating that it is a non-electrolyte. Nitrate group is therefore coordinated to the metal ion raising the coordination number to 3. This is also confirmed by infrared spectral data. The ionic and coordinated nature of nitrate group was clearly distinguished by several workers^{2,6,7} earlier based on i.r. spectra. The bands at 800(s), 950(m), 990(m) and 1155(s) cm^{-1} noticed in the dipyridyl complex are definitely due to coordinated nitrate group. The low melting point of 148° and solubility in common organic solvents also suggest the covalent nature of the complex. Thus, it is one more example of three-coordination for silver I.

The 6-phenanthroline complex has the formula $[\text{Ag}(\text{phen})_2]\text{NO}_3$. The molar conductance value in nitrobenzene is high comparable to that of a 1:1 electrolyte (~ 25 mhos). Hence nitrate group is ionic and the i.r. absorption bands are also indicative of an ionic nature for the nitrate group. The high melting point ($> 300^\circ$) and poor solubility in common organic solvents suggest also an ionic nature of the complex. Hence it is an example for tetra-coordination of silver I with two bidentate ligands bonded at four positions to the metal ion.

The 2:9 dimethyl substitution and 4:7 diphenyl substitution in 6-phenanthroline ring brings about a marked change in the coordinating ability of the ligands. Whilst the 6-phenanthroline forms a four-coordinated compound, the substituted 6-phenanthrolines give rise to apparently two-coordinated complexes. The nitrate group remains ionic as evidenced by the molar conductance and i.r. spectra. They have also high melting points and poor solubility. So, they are apparently two-coordinated.

This co-ordination number 2 giving rise to linear structures is very common in silver I complexes and they are invariably formed by the bonding of two moles of monodentate ligands. But, the complexes under report are formed by the addition of one molecule of a bidentate ligand for which there is no reported example in the literature so far. They may well be polynuclear complex ions⁸. Therefore, detailed further studies are needed before any definite conclusions are drawn in these cases.

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